

The Psalm Project

Discovering the Spiritual World through the Psalms

Psalm 92

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The Goal of this project:

This research project will examine the 150 psalms for the spiritual awareness each Psalm offers. Each Psalm will be examined by its language and the commentary of the Sages. The spiritual awareness analysis will be done in alignment with Ari's definition of the Tree of life, the Book of Creation, and the Zohar. Each verse of the Psalm will be rewritten using the intent of the language and spiritual commentary to convey its spiritual lesson.

The Main Resources:

The Zohar

The Book of Creation

Ari's writing on the Tree of Life and the Ten Sefirot

The Theological Wordbook of the Old Testament

Samson Hirsch's commentary on the Psalms

Tehillim – Psalms – A new translation with a commentary anthologized from the Talmudic and rabbinic sources

Accordance Bible Software

Psalm 92

New American Standard 1995	Hebrew
<p>Psa. 92:0 A Psalm, a Song for the Sabbath day.</p>	<p>Psa. 92:1 מְזִמּוֹר שִׁיר לַיּוֹם הַשַּׁבָּת : 2</p>
<p>Psa. 92:1 It is ^agood to give thanks to the LORD And to ^bsing praises to Your name, O Most High; ² To ^adeclare Your lovingkindness in the morning And Your ^bfaithfulness ¹by night, ³ ¹With the ^aten-stringed lute and ¹with the ^aharp, ¹With resounding music ²upon the ^alyre. ⁴ For You, O LORD, have made me glad by ¹what You ^ahave done, I will ^bsing for joy at the ^aworks of Your hands.</p>	<p>טוֹב לְהַדְרוֹת לַיהוָה וּלְזַמֵּר לְשִׁמְחָה עֲלֵיוֹן : 3 לְהַגִּיד בַּבֶּקֶר חַסְדֶּךָ וְאַמְּוֹנַתְךָ בַּלַּיְלֹת : 4 עָלֵי-עֶשׂוֹר וְעָלֵי-נֶבֶל עָלֵי הַגִּיטָרָה בְּכִנּוֹר : 5 כִּי שָׁמַחַתְנִי יְהוָה בְּפַעֲלֶךָ בְּמַעֲשֵׂי יְדֶיךָ אֲרַגֵּן : 6 מִתֶּגְדָּלְךָ מֵעַשְׂרֵי יְהוָה לֹמֵד עִמְקוֹ מִחֲשֹׁבְתֶיךָ : 7 אִישׁ-בַּעַר לֹא יֵדַע וְכִסִּיל לֹא-יָבִין אֶת-זֹאת : 8 בְּפֶרֶחַ רִשְׁעִים אֶכְמוּ וְעָשָׁב וַיִּצְצוּ כָּל-פְּעָלֵי אֹן לְהַשְׁמֵדָם עַד-יְעַד : 9 וְאַתָּה מְרוֹם לְעֵלָם יְהוָה : 10 כִּי הִנֵּה אֵיבֶיךָ יְהוָה כִּי-הִנֵּה אֵיבֶיךָ יֵאָבְדוּ יִתְפָּרְדּוּ כָּל-פְּעָלֵי אֹן : 11 וְתָרַם כְּרָאִים קִרְנֵי בִלְתֵי בְשֵׁמֶן רַעֲנָן : 12 וְתִבֵּט עֵינָי בְּשׂוֹרֵי בְקָמִים עָלַי מִרְעִים תִּשְׁמַעְנָה אֲזִנִּי : 13 צְדִיק כְּתָמַר יִפְרַח כְּאֶרֶז בַּלְבָּנוֹן יִשְׁגָּה : 14 שְׁתוּלִים בְּבַיִת יְהוָה בְּחֲצָרוֹת אֶל-הֵינִי יִפְרִיחוּ : 15 עוֹד יִנוּכּוֹן בְּשִׁיבָה דְשָׁנִים וְרַעֲנָנִים יִהְיוּ : 16 לְהַגִּיד כִּי-יֵשֶׁר יְהוָה צְלוֹרֵי וְלֹא-עֲלָתָה [עוֹלָתָה] בּוֹ :</p>
<p>Psa. 92:5 How ^agreat are Your works, O LORD! Your ^{1b}thoughts are very ^adeep. ⁶ A ^asenseless man has no knowledge, Nor does a ^astupid man understand this: ⁷ That when the wicked ^asprouted up like grass And all ^bwho did iniquity flourished, It <i>was only</i> that they might be ^adestroyed forevermore. ⁸ But You, O LORD, are ^aon high forever.</p>	<p>יְהוָה כִּי-הִנֵּה אֵיבֶיךָ יֵאָבְדוּ יִתְפָּרְדּוּ כָּל-פְּעָלֵי אֹן : 11 וְתָרַם כְּרָאִים קִרְנֵי בִלְתֵי בְשֵׁמֶן רַעֲנָן : 12 וְתִבֵּט עֵינָי בְּשׂוֹרֵי בְקָמִים עָלַי מִרְעִים תִּשְׁמַעְנָה אֲזִנִּי : 13 צְדִיק כְּתָמַר יִפְרַח כְּאֶרֶז בַּלְבָּנוֹן יִשְׁגָּה : 14 שְׁתוּלִים בְּבַיִת יְהוָה בְּחֲצָרוֹת אֶל-הֵינִי יִפְרִיחוּ : 15 עוֹד יִנוּכּוֹן בְּשִׁיבָה דְשָׁנִים וְרַעֲנָנִים יִהְיוּ : 16 לְהַגִּיד כִּי-יֵשֶׁר יְהוָה צְלוֹרֵי וְלֹא-עֲלָתָה [עוֹלָתָה] בּוֹ :</p>

⁹ For, behold, Your enemies, O LORD,

For, behold, ^aYour enemies will perish;

All who do iniquity will be ^bscattered.

Psa. 92:10 But You have exalted my ^ahorn like *that of* the wild ox;

I have ¹been ^banointed with fresh oil.

¹¹ And my eye has ^alooked *exultantly* upon ¹my foes,

My ears hear of the evildoers who rise up against me.

¹² The ^arighteous man will ¹flourish like the palm tree,

He will grow like a ^bcedar in Lebanon.

¹³ ^aPlanted in the house of the LORD,

They will flourish ^bin the courts of our God.

¹⁴ They will still ^{1a}yield fruit in old age;

They shall be ²full of sap and very green,

¹⁵ To ¹declare that ^athe LORD is upright;

He is my ^brock, and there is ^cno unrighteousness in Him.

References

Psalm 92:1

^aPs 147:1

^bPs 135:3

Psalm 92:2

¹Lit *nights*

^aPs 59:16

^bPs 89:1

Psalm 92:3

¹Lit *Upon*

²Lit *by means of*

^a1 Sam 10:5; 1 Chr 13:8; Neh 12:27; Ps 33:2

Psalm 92:4

¹Lit *Your working*

^aPs 40:5; 90:16

^bPs 106:47

^cPs 8:6; 111:7; 143:5

Psalm 92:5

¹Or *purposes*

^aPs 40:5; 111:2; Rev 15:3

^bPs 33:11; 40:5; 139:17

^cPs 36:6; Rom 11:33

Psalm 92:6

^aPs 49:10; 73:22; 94:8

Psalm 92:7

^aJob 12:6; Ps 90:5

^bPs 94:4

^cPs 37:38

Psalm 92:8

^aPs 83:18; 93:4; 113:5

Psalm 92:9

^aPs 37:20

^bPs 68:1; 89:10

Psalm 92:10

¹Or *become moist*

^aPs 75:10; 89:17; 112:9

^bPs 23:5; 45:7

Psalm 92:11

¹Or *those who lie in wait for me*

^aPs 54:7; 91:8

Psalm 92:12

¹Lit *sprout*

^aNum 24:6; Ps 1:3; 52:8; 72:7; Jer 17:8; Hos 14:5, 6

^bPs 104:16; Ezek 31:3

Psalm 92:13

^aPs 80:15; Is 60:21

^bPs 100:4; 116:19

Psalm 92:14

¹Or *thrive in*

²Lit *fat and*

^aProv 11:30; Is 37:31; John 15:2; James 3:18

Psalm 92:15

¹Or *show forth*

^aJob 34:10; Ps 25:8

^bDeut 32:4; Ps 18:2; 94:22

^cRom 9:14

Targum

Psa. 92:1 A psalm and song that the first Adam uttered concerning the Sabbath day. ² It is good to give thanks in the presence of the LORD, and to praise your name, O Most High. ³ To recount your goodness in the morning, and your truth in the nights, ⁴ According to the harp of ten strings, and according to the lyre, upon the murmuring of harps. ⁵ For you have made me glad, O LORD, by your works; I will rejoice in the works of your hands. ⁶ How great are your works, O LORD; your thoughts are very deep. ⁷ A foolish son of man will not know it, and a fool will not comprehend this. ⁸ While the wicked flourish like grass and all workers of deceit blossom, God is going to destroy them forever. ⁹ But you are high and supreme in this age, O LORD, and you are high and supreme in the age to come. [ANOTHER TARGUM: And you, your hand is supreme to punish the wicked in the age to come, in the great day of judgment, O LORD; and you, your hand is supreme to give a good reward to the righteous in the age to come, O LORD.] ¹⁰ For, behold, your enemies, O LORD, for behold, your enemies will perish in the age to come; and all the workers of deceit will be separated from the band of the righteous. ¹¹ You have raised up my might like a wild-ox; you have anointed me with moist anointing oil of the leafy olive. ¹² And my eye has looked on the perdition of my oppressors; my ear has heard the sound of the destruction of those who stand against me to do harm. ¹³ The righteous man will grow fruit like the palm-tree, like the cedar in Lebanon he will grow and produce roots. ¹⁴ His sons will be planted in the sanctuary of the LORD; in the court of the house of our God they will flourish. ¹⁵ Again like their fathers they will produce sons in old age; they will be plump and juicy. ¹⁶ So that the inhabitants of the earth might tell it, for the LORD is upright; my strength, and there is no wrong in him.

Spiritual Awareness

Introduction

The LORD completed physical creation in six days. The spiritual creation of humanity will continue until the world ends. It is unfair to judge God's equity before the denouement of human history, even though history appears to be a long series of tragic injustices. Each injustice has hopefully taught a lesson to humanity that is carried to the next generation.

On the first Shabbat, Adam surveyed the LORD's completed work and was stirred to sing of the marvelous perfection his eyes beheld. This Psalm speaks of man's bewilderment as he observes the apparent inequity in the world. It also tells of the joy he will experience when the inequities are resolved.

Verse two

To proclaim the work of the Sefirah Chesed in the morning and Your faithfulness in the nights.

Verse seven

There are evil people on earth who do not understand that materialism is only one-half of human existence. These people only believe what they can touch. Faith in the LORD requires a person to believe in something that cannot be seen, but the person knows it is there.

When the lawless spring up as the grass, where all the abusers of might flourish, that is so that they may be destroyed forever.

Verse ten

The LORD does not have to intervene with a supernatural act to destroy wicked people. The LORD wrote their destruction into the Torah, which created the Universe's fabric. Each person will have to answer for the sins they did not repent. It is best to repent for sins committed before it is too late. When the flesh dies, the rest of the soul must answer for sins. One will not have the opportunity in the LORD's court to ask for forgiveness or another chance to repent.

While you lifted by my horns like that of the wild ox, I outlive them with ever-renewed consecration.

Verse thirteen

Grass will grow anywhere by itself. Palm and cedar trees which the righteous person is compared to here, are planted deliberately in the House of the LORD. The fruit is the mitzvot that the righteous perform in the name of the LORD.

Planted in the House of God, they will flourish in the courts of our God.

Appendix

Mystical Methodology to Prayer

All prayers result in spiritual energy which rises through the conduits that connect Sefirot realms. The "answer" to prayers is the transformation of spiritual energy from its original frequency to an appropriate frequency which will give the necessary results.

Chambers of Aba and Ima of Briyah

Keter: prayers of thanksgiving come

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